

**METHODS OF TRANSLATION OF SCIENTIFIC, TECHNICAL TEXTS
AND TERMS**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7481657>

Z.A.Abdurahmanova

Teacher Uzbekistan State World Languages University

Annotation: *This article discusses some methods of translating scientific and technical texts and terms. Before working on a scientific and technical text, it is necessary to remember that grammatical and lexical conditions are accepted in the process of translation. In the article, it was said that in the translation of scientific and technical texts, it is necessary to take into account the specific nature and character of the text, and the specificity, a ma'noliness and economy of scientific and technical texts are characteristic.*

Key words: Scientific texts, technical translation, original text, translation methods, terms, information

The attention of prestigious technical higher educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan is focused on increasing the competitiveness of their graduates. For this purpose, qualified and knowledgeable specialists with relevant work experience are being recruited to teach students and masters.

The development of international relations, the two-way wide flow of technical information raises the questions of clarifying the goals and tasks of foreign language teaching in technical higher educational institutions. Therefore, great importance is attached to the translation of scientific and technical texts from a foreign language into the native language. Students and masters use the dictionary to translate technical texts that they need in work and study, such as

instructions, descriptions of machine or device tariffs, catalogs, scientific articles
Therefore, we decided to focus on the translation of technical texts.

In methods and technical texts, the objective topic prevails. First, objects and situations, information are presented. Therefore, technical texts are pragmatic texts that provide job-related information. Thus, scientific and technical translation shows the nature of data. Its purpose is primarily to convey the content of information clearly and without flaws. In technical translations, it is said that the information is accurate and the content does not change. Accuracy of information means that the amount of information contained in the original text is preserved in the translated text.

Before working on the text, it is necessary to remember that grammatical and lexical conditions are accepted in the process of translation. The lexical and grammatical function of the word is visible only in the structure of the sentence and its main importance is determined. The text determines the meaning of the word in each specific case. The different meanings of the word are interrelated and united around the general, main, main content. The meaning of the word is defined in the text in relation to other words. Therefore, in order to find the exact meaning of a word, it is necessary to see it not separately, but in connection with other words.

Translation is not a simple replacement of words in one language with equivalent words in another language. The translation of the text should be adequate, equal and suitable in all respects.

Adequate is a translation that clearly conveys the content of the original without inseparability; to the translation in which the semantic and stylistic or functional harmony of the original language tools is achieved; it means a translation that is equivalent to the intellectual content and stylistic function of the text.

Even if the content of the text being translated is the same, the form often does not match, so the translation is carried out not in form - literally, but in

content. The form of the text is determined by the language being translated, it is given as the conveyance of certain content and the expression of this or that stylistic function.

One of the main reasons for incorrect translation of a scientific text is to start looking for unfamiliar words unrelated to the context in the dictionary without knowing the content of the text. As a result, a set of translated words occurs, because the grammatical interdependence of the words in the sentence is lost. To find the right meaning of the word, you need to familiarize with the content of the text. Before translating an unfamiliar word, it is necessary to determine its grammatical form. For example, in English, for a noun - the primary form, singular form, for a verb - the simple degree. The initial form of the word is given in the dictionary as a representative of the set of words and is considered lexical.

Before looking for a word in the dictionary, it is necessary to determine which part of the sentence it belongs to according to its morphological sign and change it from the found form to the dictionary form. Before translating the text, it is necessary to review it, that is, to get acquainted with its content and theme. First of all, it is necessary to determine the type of sentence: indicative sentence, interrogative sentence, exclamatory sentence. Punctuation and word order will help in this. Then, it is necessary to determine which sentences belong to the mixed type, whether there is a change in the usual word order in this sentence, common determiners or adjectives, and so on. Word order and conjunctions help in this too.

In conclusion, when translating scientific and technical texts from a foreign language into one's native language, it is necessary to use all translation methods to provide the most accurate and complete information without changing it.

Also, in the translation of scientific and technical texts, it is necessary to take into account the specific nature and character of this text

THE LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. Elina N.P., Sadykov H.S., Working with a dictionary. - T.: TCTI, 2005
- 2 <https://www.pactranz.com/technical-translator-translating-technical-texts/>
- 3 <https://phrase.com/solutions/technical-translation/>